

Towards the uncertainty quantification of AI-models in 6G networks

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Abstract— The evolution towards the 6th generation of telecommunication systems blazes the trail for the advent of a plethora of innovative technologies that aim to radically change the current telecommunication systems. The new generation of networks is challenged to serve highly demanding applications and services that are hosted in a substantial number of devices. The complexity of the new telecommunication ecosystems has designated the adoption of AI solutions as inevitable in order to conduct fundamental network operations such as resource management and orchestration. However, the AI models are not always able to provide certain estimates, and they may suffer from under- or over- confidence in their predictions. With a view to tackling this issue, in this work, we employ an innovative framework aiming to quantify the uncertainty in the estimates predicted via two DL models, i.e., the LSTM and the 1D-CNN, which are trained with telecommunication data. It is shown that the uncertainty quantification procedure is a strong aspect in designing trustworthy AI models since it increases the probability that the actual predictions are within the interval of the model predictions.

Keywords— 6G networks, AI uncertainty quantification, model calibration, conformal inference, AWS-Fortuna

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of the Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the noticeable growth of innovative fields such as Robotics give the prominence to the development of innovative technologies such as e-health and Augmented Reality (AR) / Virtual Reality (VR) or even large technological ecosystems such as Smart Cities. Critical economical sectors such as the Industrial Manufacturing and the Transportations are going to undergo revolutionary changes as their processes are going to be driven to fully automated. The seamless operation of these factors entails the existence of a telecommunication infrastructure able to provide high data rates, low latency and relentless connectivity. The telecommunication infrastructure that is anticipated to serve as the catalyst to the transformation of these fields is the 6th generation (6G) of communication networks. Contrary to the previous generations of telecommunication systems that provide services for

Human-to-Human (H2H) communication, the 6G networks aim to expand the cycle of communication in order to include the Machine-to-Machine (M2M) communication [1].

However, the abovementioned systems constitute complex environments that are based on the interaction and cooperation of multiple applications hosted by a substantial number of devices. With a view to perform efficiently, each application has specific requirements both in communication and computational resources that should be fulfilled by the network infrastructure. On the other hand, the network resources are finite, so the necessity emerges for the accurate determination of the resource assignment to the applications. For this reason, the Service Level Agreements (SLAs) between the network service providers and the application users were introduced. An SLA constitutes a legal and detailed contract that typically determines the service quality provided to the application users, the responsibilities of both parties and the penalties in case of SLA violation [2]. Therefore, the network service provider is obliged to distribute the system's resources to the application users according to the terms and conditions defined in the SLA contract.

The modern telecommunication systems are challenged to serve a vast number of users, with diverse requirements and different capabilities. Since the resource assignment procedure in these systems is quite complex, the classic methods for resource allocation cannot deal with these intensified conditions. For this reason, the resource allocation in beyond 5G networks will be mainly conducted with the aid of AI models [3], [4]. AI models constitute a strong ally in system resource management as they are able to provide efficient solutions to perplexing problems in significantly low time. However, the AI models are characterized as black box methods and consequently they lack transparency and trust. It is a common issue in the literature that in many cases the AI models are not able to provide certain estimates, which may suffer from under or over confidence [5].

Accordingly, when the resource management is considered, this can be interpreted as resource under- or over-provisioning to the users [6]. In case of resource under-provisioning, the allocated resources do not suffice in order to serve a user's request causing Quality of Service (QoS) degradation. A severe QoS degradation experienced by the user constitutes a strong factor that violates the SLA between the service provider and the user. An SLA violation is associated with a penalty at the expense of the service provider, and it may induce large financial costs. On the other hand, in the case of resource over-provisioning, the resources that are allocated to serve a user are more than those required causing underutilization of the available resources. Even though the resource under-utilization has not as a severe impact as an SLA violation, the substandard resource exploitation may induce undesirable indirect gain loss to the service provider. This relies on the fact that the unexploited system resources could be assigned in order to serve a larger number of users. As a consequence, it is an essential requirement to develop reliable and trustworthy AI models that diminish the uncertainty in their predictions.

To deal with this issue, in this work we utilize two Deep Learning (DL) models, i.e., a long short-term memory (LSTM) and a convolutional neural network (CNN) in order to conduct time series forecasting in data generated from a telecommunication system. Next, we employ the framework proposed in [7] that calibrates the predictions of the two DL models in order to decrease the uncertainty in their estimates. Finally, we quantify the uncertainty that was introduced by the two models before the calibration procedure. To the best of our knowledge, our work constitutes the first work that employs a method for model calibration and uncertainty quantification in order to improve the performance of DL models associated with telecommunication data.

The remainder of this paper is the following: In Section II we present the employed methodology for the quantification of the uncertainty in the model estimates. In Section III, we provide a dataset description while in Section IV we present the methods that were utilized in our analysis. In Section V the numerical results obtained via the proposed framework are demonstrated and we conclude in Section VI.

II. UNCERTAINTY QUANTIFICATION IN TELECOMMUNICATION SYSTEMS

In recent years, AI models, and especially the DL models, have penetrated into various and critical fields of science. Their capability of dealing with challenging issues and providing efficient solutions has designated them as an indispensable factor in a plethora of applications. However, despite the remarkable performance observed in terms of accuracy, the DL models suffer from under- and over-confidence in their estimates. To tackle this issue, many researchers in the academia move towards on understanding the factors that introduce the uncertainty in the predictions of a deep neural network (DNN) and on proposing methods for its quantification [8].

Apropos the telecommunication systems, the evolution towards the 6G networks blazes the trail for incorporating the AI models in order to manage critical network functions such as resource management or network orchestration. The designing procedure of the 6G networks aims on developing fully automated systems that can serve an enormous number of users in a cost-effective manner. Therefore, the necessity emerges for being able to quantify and calibrate the uncertainty in the model estimates with a view to developing trustworthy DL models.

For this reason, in this work we aim to employ an innovative framework in order to quantify the uncertainty in the estimates predicted via two DL models trained with telecommunication data. In more detail, the utilized dataset includes historical time stamped records about the arrival and the departure of requests related to three types of services: SMS, Internet and calls. Our purpose is to exploit some of the records in order to predict the corresponding values in the next time slot; thus, our problem can be dealt with as a time series forecasting problem. Keeping that in mind, we utilized two DL model architectures in order to conduct our predictions: an LSTM neural network and a CNN. In regard to the former type of neural network, the LSTM constitutes the most prominent DL model architecture for time series forecasting as it is able to acquire knowledge of information over extended time intervals. This attribute is vital in time series forecasting problems since recognizing the context and dependencies across time in the data is critical. On the other hand, the CNN network architecture is mainly exploited in the literature for image processing and object recognition tasks. However, the CNNs excel in recognizing patterns and hierarchical features in data, designating them effective in capturing complex temporal dependencies existing in time series data.

Regarding the uncertainty quantification procedure, a set of methodologies based on the probability and statistical theory are newly developed for dealing with both epistemic and aleatoric uncertainty, mostly in DL models. For instance, Bayesian deep learning combines Bayesian probabilistic principles with DL for that purpose. In our methodology, we follow a more traditional approach that is based on frequentist statistics, and generates confidence bounds in the set of DL modeling outputs, using as paradigm the topic of time series forecasting. In particular, with a view to conducting uncertainty quantification in the estimates generated via the two DL models, we employ the methodology presented in Fig.1, which consists of the following steps [7]:

1) *Model outputs prediction*: This step refers to the procedure according to which the DL models, i.e. in our case the LSTM and the CNN, are trained in order to provide solutions for specific tasks. During the training procedure, each DL model is able to learn the correlation between the input data and the corresponding outputs. When the training procedure is completed, the DL models are able to predict the output for each input data related to

the task. In addition, for each predicted output in this step two probabilistic parameters are also calculated: a) the centrality metric (i.e. the mean value) and b) the dispersion metric (i.e. the standard deviation) of the predicted value. These parameters are necessary for the model calibration and the conformal inference procedures.

Fig. 1: Employed methodology for uncertainty quantification.

2) *Model calibration*: The calibration of the confidence interval of the DL models refers to the process that aims to prevent the model's posterior distribution from being under- or over-confident. In particular, model calibration is generally the procedure that adjusts a DL model to warrant that its outcome (characterized by an amount of uncertainty) meets the true likelihood of the predicted event. Therefore, the validation process constitutes a mandatory step that should not be omitted while it designates the need to evolve the modelling process into probabilistic. In respect to the methods for calibration, in our analysis we employed the temperature scaling method, which is special and simplified category of the Platt scaling technique [9]. As a consequence, the calibration procedure plays a vital role in developing reliable and trustworth DL models that can be exploited in order to handle challenging tasks necessary for the operation of the 6G networks [10].

3) *Conformal inference*: Conformal inference is generally the process of creating statistically valid (conformal) intervals to quantify the uncertainty of the predictions of a model [11]. Technically speaking, we utilize as inputs in this step the credible prediction intervals of validation set and test set forecasts, and the validation set actual values. In our experiments, conformal prediction is held via conformal quantile regression [12].

III. DATASET DESCRIPTION

For the purpose of conducting our analysis, we exploit the dataset in [13], which contains time series data of activity of telecommunications from the city of Milan. In this context, the city has been spatially divided into 10000 square grids, and data generated from internet, SMS, and calls activity are recorded from 01/11/2013 to 01/01/2014 with 10-minute resolution. Each value in the data is a call detail record (CDR); i.e., a specific instance of a telecommunication transaction that passes through a network element. It is worth mentioning that this dataset constitutes a representative real-world example, fitting

perfectly to the application of our experimentation since the majority of telecommunication data generated in modern telecommunication networks are basically related to these three services. In addition, the dataset is characterized by a non-trivial pattern throughout its time progression (in terms of trend, seasonality, outlier presence, etc.), posing an additional challenge in the DL modeling procedure. Finally, by inspecting the dataset, it becomes apparent that three distinct time series can be produced with aggregating operations: internet, SMS (summing in and out), and calls (summing in and out). A data aggregation in a 1-hour resolution was performed in order to generate time series that are more appropriate for modeling, e.g., being rendered more robust to noise, being able to capture a trend pattern and a seasonal pattern, etc. In addition, due to the fact that the size of the original dataset of the city of Milan is huge, we utilized in our analysis for simplification purposes only a part of its records, which corresponds to the traffic generated in one region of the city of Milan with the unique identifier "5059".

IV. THE EMPLOYED FRAMEWORK

With a view to developing reliable DL-models that are capable for performing efficient time series forecasting, the employed framework is based on the methodology described in Section II and consists of the following steps: First of all, the dataset preprocessing procedure occurs, where univariate forecasting techniques were employed. The time series are split without shuffling in a 60%-20%-20% train-validation-test partition. Next, the train and validation subsets were utilized in the training procedure and the test subset was excluded in order to preserve the model unbiased. It is important to mention that the role of the validation set is two-fold: i) for hyperparameter tuning of the employed forecasting engines, i.e., the DL models, and ii) for generating validation uncertainties that are needed in future steps. Prior to modelling time series forecasting, data are scaled in the interval of $[0, 1]$ with min-max scaling. Second, the time series forecasting process takes place which includes the DL-model training procedure and the predicted outputs inference. Finally, the output estimates uncertainty quantification (i.e., the calibration and the conformal inference) is performed by employing the package of AWS-Fortuna [14]. In more detail, the development of the proposed framework was held in Python 3.8, mainly incorporating features of the TensorFlow 2.1 package [15], and the AWS-Fortuna package [14]. Overall, the whole conception that is described in the relatively recent AWS-Fortuna paper in [7] was highly motivational and inspirational with regard to the framework that we propose and operated as a guide in our analysis for quantifying uncertainty in the DL models.

A. Time series forecasting

As previously mentioned, in our analysis the LSTM model [16] and 1-dimensional CNN (1D-CNN) [17] were implemented and applied for the time series forecasting task. In addition, the development of the DL models was

conducted according to the procedure proposed in [18], which also indicates that utilization of DL methods overwhelms empirically traditional time series forecasting algorithms, such as ARIMA. A central adjustment of ours in both cases is that we aim to produce probabilistic (that originate from a normal distribution) samples and compute the mean and variance, instead of forecasting a single value. Therefore, the exploited models can also be referred to as probabilistic LSTM and 1D-CNN, respectively.

1) *The LSTM*: The LSTM is a familiar option for time series forecasting, given that DL is about to be used. In our application, we use a primary layer of 64 nodes, a secondary layer of 32 nodes, and a final layer of 2 nodes (corresponding to the mean and the standard deviation of the estimated normal distribution). Furthermore, between successive layers a dropout of 20% is performed, and all layers make use of the “ReLU” gate. The standard deviation is assured as strictly positive with a “SoftPlus” gate. The learning rate was set equal to 0.001, and the number of training epochs was set equal to 50. All details and hyperparameters in the application were assessed experimentally for optimality.

2) *The 1D-CNN*: The 1D-CNN is a usual DL-based alternative of LSTM for time series forecasting. Similarly, in our application, we use a primary layer of 64 filters, a secondary layer of 32 filters, and a final layer of 2 nodes (corresponding to the mean and the standard deviation of the estimated normal distribution). Between successive layers a dropout of 20% is performed, and all layers make use of the “ReLU” gate. The standard deviation is assured as strictly positive with a “SoftPlus” gate. The learning rate was set equal to 0.001, and the number of training epochs was set equal to 50. Similar to the LSTM, all details and hyperparameters in the application were assessed experimentally for optimality.

It is worth mentioning that the final layer was added in both DL models for the calculation of the two probabilistic parameters (i.e. the mean value and the standard deviation) that are required for the model calibration and the conformal inference procedures. Therefore, the impact of the uncertainty quantification procedure in the computational complexity of the DL models can be considered as negligible and consequently the whole process complexity is dominated by the time required for training the neural network. The evaluation of the developed DL-models is held according to a common technique in the field of time series analysis, known as “rolling window” validation procedure, and we denote that a training window of size 5, and a forecast horizon of step 1. In addition, to estimate the accuracy of the developed DL models, we utilize the following typical validation metrics: a) the root of mean squared error (RMSE), b) the mean absolute error (MAE) and c) the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE). It is important to note that prior to calculating those metrics, historical data and forecasts are descaled at the original scale.

B. Uncertainty quantification

Appropos the uncertainty quantification of DL outputs, as it is described in Section II, two key techniques are utilized for quality control of the predictions yielded by sophisticated opaque AI-based models: namely, calibration and conformal inference. The AWS-Fortuna framework that was adopted for the employment of the uncertainty quantification tasks is designed to either run originally a Flax DL model with Bayesian principles [19] or join in the output of a probabilistic DL model for prediction. We proceed with the latter approach that is followed by calibrating the yielded uncertainties and generating conformal interval sets.

The evaluation of model calibration aims to maximize the prediction log-probability (minimize the opposite), while in conformal inference we attempt to maximize the prediction interval coverage probability (PICP) of the test forecast, with the minimal margin of error (ME). Notice that we usually express indeterminate continuous values as mean \pm ME, and that increasing ME obviously increases the PICP, which in fact is a metric that denotes the percent of test actual values contained within the test forecast intervals. Finally, all the aforementioned properties rely consistently on the defined confidence level, like 90%, 95% and 99%.

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

It can be experimentally detected in our dataset that there occurs an imminent relationship between three types of outcomes in this study: the forecasting error, the success of calibration, and the quality of conformal inference (and, thus, the quality of the uncertainty quantification process). In this section, a numerical analysis is presented that illustrates this relationship, as well as a demonstration that attempts to capture the essence of how a process of uncertainty quantification may work in practical scenarios, as described in Section IV. Table I illustrates the evaluation of forecasting in our experiments, using the previously mentioned validation metrics for prediction of scale values. Notice that when zeros exist in the test dataset (symbolized with an asterisk below), the MAPE metric excludes the corresponding time points in computation and thus the MAPE computation is not affected by these values. According to the estimated errors below, LSTM overcomes 1D-CNN in all instances of time series forecasting in our experiments.

Fig. 2 exposes the relationship between the anticipated credible confidence of forecasting and conformal inference (x-axis) and the actual PICP achieved with forecasting and the generated conformal intervals (y-axis) in the test set. In specific, we apply a conformal inference process to both calibrated and non-calibrated estimates in order to show the impact of the calibration process in the models’ expected confidence. In particular, a conformal inference process receives as input the uncertainty estimates of the outputs of any DL model in the validation set, which are either calibrated or not, along with an expected error (or alternatively, a confidence) in the test set. Next, it outputs the corresponding conformal

intervals for the test set values, given the expected confidence.

TABLE I. EVALUATION METRICS OF THE UNIVARIATE FORECASTING PROCESS

Univariate forecasting evaluation				
data	model	RMSE	MAE	MAPE
Internet	LSTM	1274	800	31%
	1D-CNN	1664	1072	43%
SMS	LSTM	589	192	64%
	1D-CNN	1037	257	85%
call	LSTM	239	119	56%*
	1D-CNN	410	172	87%*

Fig. 2: Expected confidence of prediction and conformal inference vs PICP for calibrated and non-calibrated DL models

Fig. 3 reveals the relationship between the acquired normalized ME (i.e., the ME been divided with the mean of the time series test values), and the actual PICP achieved with forecasting and the generated conformal intervals (y-axis) in the test set. Our target is to provide an optimal trade-off among the depicted metrics, since a combination of the minimal ME with the maximal achieved actual PICP is highly desirable. Overall, the choices regarding all three values under study (i.e., internet, SMS, call), both two forecasting engines (LSTM or 1D-CNN), and both two calibration options (i.e., with and without calibrations) are comprehensively combined and jointly evaluated. Expected confidence receives all values from 80% to 99% with step 1%.

Fig.3: Normalized prediction and conformal inference ME vs PICP for calibrated and non-calibrated DL models

It is easily observed in Figs.2-3 that the model calibration always improves the actual PICP, irrespective of the dataset, the forecasting engine, or the expected significances. In particular, there is always a dotted line strictly above the corresponding (either red - LSTM, or green - 1D-CNN) solid line, verifying that fact. Obviously, as the expected confidence level increases, the actual PICP is increased concurrently. In calibrated models and as smaller the forecasting error is, the actual PICP achieved is always much higher than the anticipated calibration confidence.

In the same manner, the actual PICP is increased with the increase of the ME. This is reasonable since the increase in the ME increases the probability that the predicted values will be within the interval of the actual test set values. Moreover, it is shown that the relationship between the ME and PICP is not linear, and there always exists a threshold of ME after which PICP stays almost constant. For example, in Fig.3 it is easily inquired that for the minimal ME yielding to an actual PICP of 95% or bigger (see the dashed horizontal black line). The forecasting success is almost always related to better ME-PICP tradeoffs, with an exception at the experiment of the SMS time series and the 1D-CNN forecasting engine, which is probably due to the existence of a large outlier in the test set of the SMS time series. In specific, it was observed that outcomes of uncertainty quantification show a most appropriate pattern in the case of 1D-CNN instead of LSTM, but LSTM performs better given the forecasting evaluation. This generic concept holds for calibrated

(dotted lines) and uncalibrated (solid lines) models, as yielded in Figs. 2-3.

From a network engineering point of view, being able to determine the optimal trade-off between the ME and PICP metrics and consequently to guarantee a forecasting success gives us the potentiality to provide trustworthy estimates about the network operations. In particular, improving the actual PICP through model calibration improves the probability that the predicted output values correspond to the true values indicating that network operations such as resource allocation will be conducted without resource under- or over-provisioning to the users.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented an innovative framework in order to quantify the uncertainty in the estimates predicted via two DL models i.e., the LSTM and the CNN, trained with telecommunication data. The employed methodology consists of the three distinct steps: 1) the model outputs prediction, 2) the estimates calibration and 3) the conformal inference. It is shown that the uncertainty quantification procedure significantly improves the probability that the actual values are within the interval of the predicted values. In addition, a better trade-off between the minimization of marginal error in the predictions and the maximization of prediction interval coverage probability is achieved when the model estimates are calibrated. As a future work, we aim to utilize this framework in order to develop strategies for efficient resource management in 6G networks.

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